

**A NEW BUSINESS MODEL
BASED ON CROWDSOURCING:
“THE CROWDLIVING COMMUNITY”**

by

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we investigate the concept of crowdsourcing and its application within local communities. Specifically, the paper addresses how crowdsourcing can benefit local businesses within a community; how individual homeowners can use bargaining power to source deals for contract work; and outlines the challenges of connecting quality contractors to the local community for the efficient deployment of their goods and services.

Research will identify the issues and limitations of crowdsourcing, a comparison and evaluation of similar business methods and proposes a new business model crowdsourcing in the context of local communities. The content will examine the opportunities crowdsourcing provides and problems that need to be solved through a comparative analysis of the market. The new business model plan will develop a platform to connect customers and local contractors (C2C). A mutual benefit to both parties is that the platform provides a secure and safe forum to conduct business in. Both the customers and contractors will benefit from the time saved using this more efficient search method. **The project name will be “A New Business Model based on Crowdsourcing: The CrowdLiving Community”**. A wireframe demo will be developed to demonstrate the platform functionality and accessibility to users.

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THE CROWDLIVING COMMUNITY

Introduction of Crowdsourcing

Web technologies have provided a variety of opportunities to develop new decision-making approaches for developers. The term “Web 2.0” was first introduced at 1999 and later became widely promoted by Tim O’Reilly at the O’Reilly Media Web 2.0 Conference of 2004. DiNucci predicted that web technologies are not just displayed or limited to a desktop computer; web can be used on a television, car’s dashboard, cellular phone, and hand-held types of devices such as tablets. Rosen writes “O’Reilly defined Web 2.0 as a collaborative, interactive, participative version of the Web where individuals were no longer passive users of content that other had posted, but were the one generating the content themselves.” (Rosen, 2011)

O’Reilly stated that a Web 2.0 application is continually updated software that improves as more people submit their contributions to consume and remix the data from multiple sources. (Alborsa, Ramosb & Hervasa, 2008) Crowdsourcing is one of the Web 2.0 technologies that are changing the way that business operates to interact, participate and sources solutions for collaboration between the individuals and companies.

This paper includes research on identified issues of crowdsourcing, comparison and evaluation of similar business methods and presents a new business model.

The content will examine the opportunities crowdsourcing provides and problems that need to be solved through a comparative analysis of the market. The new business model plan will develop a platform to connect customers and local contractors (C2C). A mutual benefit to both parties is that the platform provides a secure and safe forum to conduct business through. Both the customers and contractors will benefit from the time saved using this method, which provides a more efficient search for services.

What is Crowdsourcing?

In a 2006 Wired Magazine article, crowdsourcing was defined as a new web-based business model by the following definition “...*the act of a company or institution taking a function once performed by employees and outsourcing it to an undefined (and generally large) network of people in the form of an open call. This can take the form of peer-production (when the job is performed collaboratively), but is also often undertaken by sole individuals. The crucial prerequisite is the use of the open call format and the large network of potential laborers.*” (Howe, 2006)

The types of **CROWD Technologies** that currently exist on the market, can be subdivided according to the following categories: crowdfunding, crowdsourced design, and crowdwisdom.

Crowdfunding: mainly pertains to projects that need to collect funding for

development and fundraising from a large group of people which is similar to most charity events. For example, Kickstarter funds millions of dollars of projects from movies to gadgets types of ideas and all the funds coming from people interested in supporting the project. (Keller, Parvanta & Roth, 2013)

Crowdsourced design is the process of achieving solutions, ideas, or content by a large group of people from an online community. It combines the efforts of numerous self-identified volunteers or part-time workers, where each contributor of their own initiative adds a small portion to better the achieved result. The winner's ideas may receive a certain amount of compensation depending on the platforms that setup the crowdsourcing questions. The term "crowdsourcing" is a combination of "crowd" and "outsourcing" which refers to outsourcing ideas from an undefined public source rather than being commissioned from a specific named group.

Crowdwisdom: a platform that allows users to ask questions in front of a large pool of people who are willing to answer. The InnoCentive is a community where large corporations post technical or scientific problems for people to give their opinions or input on, from a field of experts who can help to solve the questions. (Keller, Parvanta & Roth, 2013)

Crowdsourcing model: provides a platform to collect creative/possible solutions from a distributed group of network, which allows individual users to call for

proposals to solve an issue and gather ideas while offering monetary compensation. (Caron & Chanal, 2010)

Rosen examined two frameworks and four conditions of crowdsourcing decision-making that must be present in order to succeed. (Rosen, 2011)

The foundation of the two frameworks comes into two stages; the first stage funnels down possible solutions and the second stage evaluates these solutions (Rosen, 2011). Each of the stages during the decision making process can be susceptible to problems and these problems must be eliminated in order for the crowdsourcing effort to be successful.

The four main conditions crucial to the decision-making process are:

1. Diversity of opinions

The organization is choosing decision-makers who have opinions and skill sets that may be different from their employee base and/or are seeking opinions different from the professionals of a given industry. This will depend on the decision of the organization and the contents of the issue.

2. Independent decision-making

The decision-makers are not interacting with one another during the idea generation process: *“Independence lessens the impact of group decision-making biases such as groupthink, where the decision-makers focus is on one solution without considering viable alternatives”* (Janis, 1982).

However sometimes independence of thought leading to a solution can be considered an advantages.

3. Decentralization

Decentralization relates to the mechanism (e.g. back end), through which results and communications will be handled and shared between crowd participants. Decision-makers should should share the final results of the information with the crowd (the participants). However, many organizations will keep the resulting information private; the organization should be open with their results and include the participants in the knowledge gained from the process. (Janis, 1982)

4. Mechanism to aggregate solution

Once the solution has been generated, there must be some mechanism present to aggregate the solution for review by the crowd (which also relates to back end). Once the crowd, or a group of internal experts is presented with a list of viable alternatives, the final decisions can be reached collectively.

UNDERSTAND THE EXISTING APPROACHES OF CROWDSOURCING

Crowdsourcing has existed since 2006. There are four categories of approaches that are currently being used in the market and the examples are separated in Rosens' article into four different types: *general individual business, brand initiatives that allow for customer customization, brand-sponsored initiatives and brand-sponsored competitions and challenges.* (Rosen, 2011)

1. Individual business:

Create My Tattoo (<http://www.createmytattoo.com>)

It connects users with a community of over 18,000 custom tattoo designers from all over the world. These designers compete to create your perfect custom tattoo design based on your specifications. Each tattoo design request will receive over ten variations from the multiple tattoo designers. Users can even provide feedback during the process so that designers can modify their designs during the contest. Also, users are promised a 100% satisfaction or money back guaranteed. The minimum amount of each design prize is \$20 and up.

Tattoo designers own their own copyright; they are allowed to remove any of their designs at anytime. Designers receive a 75% commission on every sale and get paid on the first of every month for tattoo designs sold the month prior (\$25.00 minimum payout). Any monthly commissions that do not meet the minimum payout amount roll over to the next month.

iStockphoto (<http://www.istockphoto.com/>)

iStockphoto is a web-based company that sells royalty-free stock photographs, illustrations, animations and video clips. Users generate the web's original royalty-free stock sources. Whether you are a user, designer, advertiser, entrepreneur or blogger, this site provides millions of affordable images, vectors graphics and video clips.

There are several requirements in order to become a contributing photographer. One must fill out an online form with proof of identification and submit three photographs for judging by the iStockphoto staff. The judging process is fairly relaxed; photographs are required to be in focus, and technically sound (regardless of their content). Photos are stored in the databases under keywords.

Credits must be purchased by users in order to buy images, the price per credit is equivalent to \$1 per 1 credit. The typical purchase price for a web sized, and web resolution royalty free iStockphoto photo ranges from one to five credits. High-resolution photographs, oversized images or longer video clips can cost up to 50 credits per item.

A typical user and photographer on the site will receive 20% of the purchase price from any of their downloaded images. Many of the

photographers are involved in the community. They help with screening of photographer applicants and maintain the database. These photographers/users who help the site can earn exclusive contracts that receive 40% of the price of their work sold on iStockphoto.

Threadless (<https://www.threadless.com>)

Threadless is a T-shirt design business, which uses crowdsourcing method to gather members of the Threadless community to submit T-shirt designs online for competition. The designs are then put to a public vote. Only a small percentage of submissions are selected to be printed and sold through an online store. Threadless was “selling 60,000 T-shirts a month” and had profit margin of 35% and was track to gross \$18 million in 2006 with only “fewer than 20 employees” (Howe, 2006).

It is a free membership community which allows anyone to join with a valid email address to verify the users' identities. Registration for memberships grants users access into the crowd where they can vote on designs or submit them. The voting process is open for two weeks for participants to vote for the best design, the process rates designs on a zero to five scale with an option to check an “I'd buy it” box and a new design to be scored becomes available to the community for sales. During an average week, at least three design will be for sale on the website. Winning designers will receive \$1500 in cash and \$500 Threadless store credit or gift certificates

that allows user to send it to friends. However, in the article by Brabham, he writes that \$2000 is a very low rate for design that has such high profits. (Brabham, 2008)

2. Brand initiatives that allow for customer customization:

LEGO Design byME (<http://idd.lego.com/en-us/subpages/designbyme/?domainredir=designbyme.lego.com>)

It allows users to create their own customized Lego sets and be able to order it through LEGO online or in stores, however the overall Design byME experience has struggled to live up to the quality standards of LEGO. Subsequently, LEGO stopped this service in January 2012 because LEGO was not able to control the design quality.

MojaMix (<http://www.mojamix.com>)

Mojamix is an online granola manufacturing system that allows users access to Premium Custom-Mixed Cereal. Users can create their own cereal combinations with cereals, dried fruits, nuts and seeds. The company packages up the clients' order and sends it to their home via first class mail. The average 12-ounce bag costs about \$12.

Nike ID (http://www.nike.com/us/en_us/c/nikeid)

NIKEiD is a service provided by Nike allowing customers to customize shoes and accessories purchased from Nike. The customer becomes the

designer as they change and add a personal look and feel to a selected item. Nike offers online services and physical NIKEiD studios in different countries around the world including: United Kingdom, Italy, France, Spain, Germany, China and the USA.

3. Brand-sponsored initiatives:

BMW (<https://www.bmwgroup-cocreationlab.com/cocreation/project/customer-innovation-lab>)

Customer Innovation Lab 1045 allows users to submit ideas to the company to improve its automobiles with regards to innovative telematics, online services, and the future design of driver assistance systems. The participants make suggestions on the website which has a structured multimedia environment that enable all users to view, evaluate and build upon proposals made by other participants. Any participant with a selected idea has the opportunities to elaborate together with other selected users.

Registered users can access all currently running projects directly from the website. For all topics that match the users' interests, the user can immediately start sharing their ideas about the futures of BMW automotives.

Internal experts [of BMW](#) will review the ideas of the Co-Creation Lab to evaluate and analyze trends, ideas, and needs concerning the respective

project. They will determine any applicable ideas from the Co-Creation Lab and will be presented to users outside of the BMW group in an anonymous form. Information about the participant will not be revealed, it will remain anonymous the participants IP-address will be stored for a period of 14 days for guarantee a correct data processing; afterwards it will be completely removed. User data is collected and evaluated in an anonymous form for further analysis for the respective project.

BMW is using crowdsourcing to collect ideas from their loyal customers and other car enthusiasts who are interested in sharing automotive ideas without offering compensation.

Proctor & Gamble (http://www.pg.com/en_CA/)

The program Connect & Develop allows customers to submit product ideas to the company. (Rosen, 2011) P&G established the program to ensure that the company's business innovation leaders consider external expertise and multiple stakeholders' perspectives. By involving ideas from the outside users, P&G can ensure their ideas stay fresh and new while providing opportunities for external users in technology development.

Starbucks (<http://mystarbucksidea.force.com>)

"My Starbucks Idea" allows users to share their ideas into three major

categories to tell the company what they think of other people's ideas and join the discussion. The three categories are *product*, *experience* and *involvement ideas*. At the time the Rosen article was published, Starbucks received approximately 115,000 ideas with a majority of those pertaining to product suggestions. (Rosen, 2011) Some of the crowdsourced ideas that have been implemented into the stores include being able to pay using a Smartphone instead of cash, a free beverage of choice on the user's birthday (for loyalty card holders), countless new coffee flavors and making ice cubes out of coffee instead of water for better flavor in its iced beverages. (Rosen, 2011)

4. Brand-sponsored competitions/challenges:

Netflix Prize (<http://www.netflixprize.com>)

Netflix was building their movie recommendation system to use algorithms to seek information to predict and improve the accuracy of how many people were going to enjoy a movie based on their movie preferences.

The campaign was really success and received so much publicity. The prize offered programmers a \$1 million grand prize (Netflix Prize – Index, 2011) the contest attracted real groups of experts in the areas of the mathematical modeling and computer programming. "Netflix established the clear rules that ownership of the submitted idea, who could participate, how the submissions would be judged, and how participants would be

compensated.” (Netflix Prize – Index, 2011)

Because of the considerable prize amount, 41,305 teams entered from 186 different countries. This led to a wealth of diversity in opinions on how to build a recommendation system for Netflix. “Actual Netflix customer data stripped of its identifying features, was used in the contest so that participants had the same information as company employees who were also presumably trying to improve the recommendation system.” (Rosen, 2011) This proved the ideas that mentioned earlier of decentralized information. The best ideas proposed by the teams were aggregated into a final algorithm by the Netflix Prize Leaderboard. In the case of Netflix, the company has successfully demonstrated how to use crowdsourcing effort to provide a solution for creating a recommendation system.

General Pros and Cons of a smaller scale project

The main advantages are the lower cost of expenses on labours and the high volume numbers of people who are ready to work for the companies/individuals at anytime. In addition, completing simple tasks by using crowdsourcing to hire cheap labour will help smaller scale companies to accomplish their tasks.

The disadvantages of hiring cheap labour may result in a less credible product, as compared to hiring professionals outside of the crowdsourcing process.

Conversely by paying professionals, they will provide with their expertise and experience for the companies. “With the crowdsourcing also comes the issue of management. There are most cases the companies have to manage a large scale of workers, which pretty much waste more of your time for management instead of solution. Besides, it’s difficult for collaboration between crowd members as they compete with each other in nature” (Stevens, 2011). Another disadvantage is that there are no contracts used in most crowdsourcing cases. Workers can quit any time during the process and the designs sold might be reused at anytime.

Define the technical problems/issues of Crowdsourcing

Crowdsourcing is an engaging way of finding solutions to difficult technical problems which is why many companies have chosen this approach. Some of these companies choose to engage directly with the crowd while other companies use intermediaries or ‘expert networks’ to run the crowdsourcing platforms as a product.

Crowdsourcing seems like a great solution to put your company’s problem out on certain networks with large amount of participants, and wait for the masses to figure out the solution. However many companies have discovered that there are unforeseen and challenging issues that they may encounter while engaging in these crowdsourcing efforts. In some cases, these challenges completely defeat the benefits of using crowdsourcing; it may potentially result in an unfulfilled

promise and disappointing the corporate team who had both high hopes and high expectations.

The following examples are six typical technical problems that will be identified and analyzed, then the potential solutions to resolve these problems will be addressed and discussed.

Problem #1: Lack of confidentiality

Crowdsourcing usually involves a large group of people who are unknown to the companies. Companies keep their crowdsourced problems simple and non-descript for fear of participant's breaching their confidentiality agreements and leaking sensitive information to other competitor companies.

Companies can request that participants sign a non-disclosure agreement, however the companies still would not be able to confirm that confidentiality has been upheld by any of the participants. *"There is only a certain amount of confidence that you can have in a large, anonymous group like this, and from a practical perspective this means that you need to hold back important information that could otherwise help them solve your problem – and this negatively affects the quality and scope of solutions that you receive"* (Wagorn, 2014).

Practical technologies need to be developed to build tools that can help to leverage the strength of the diversity of a crowd with better control over

confidentiality. In result, the companies would be able to enhance the disclosure of information in order to be able to protect them with important information which will lead the solutions to be much more on the target, and the solutions becomes more actionable and valuable.

Problem #2: Lack of communication

When a company reaches out using crowdsourcing to a group of people, which in many cases the group size is usually quite large. The company's ability to accurately describe and communicate their problem is affected by the number of people participating. The failure to effectively communicate blocks the participants from gaining a deep understanding of the problem that they are there to solve. Unfortunately if the participants don't understand the problem they will not be able to create a solution.

In a typical crowdsourcing scenario, no matter how well the problem statement is drafted, the result is still a one-sided conversation. The result is that participants that are working to solve your problem are left to make assumptions, and these assumptions can lead to off-target and out of scope solutions.

Problem #3: Risk of Intellectual Property (IP) contamination

The threat of IP contamination is incredibly hazardous to the crowdsourcing process. A company may receive lots of potential solutions during the process but afterwards the company must invest time and resources in researching that

the intellectual property of a potential solution suggested by a participant isn't contaminated (which would render the idea useless).

Companies need to identify and define intellectual property for the individuals participating in their crowdsourcing process. There are numerous submissions during a crowdsourcing event and every suggested solution could make its way into a potential invention. In order to retain the intellectual property rights to a solution, the company needs to ensure that the participants sign an agreement to release the intellectual property.

Companies need to make sure that none of the participants' future work infringes on any of the rejected solutions, or risks exposure to an infringement lawsuit.

Companies require a model that significantly reduces the exposure to IP contamination while at the same time accessing the very best solutions from participants. "The crowdsourcing campaign should include terms that give the rights to every submitted idea (which will seem unfair to participants who are not paid for their idea), this quickly becomes unmanageable" (Wagon, 2014).

Problem #4: IP that isn't clean

When the intellectual property that submitted is disruptive, unsolicited, and in some cases the ideas are not original. An example scenario is when a company engages in a crowdsourcing event for a solution to a technical problem. It requires sending out the challenge and expected to receive many responses.

One of the solutions is seemingly perfect; it provides the low-cost, unique and disruptive solution to the problem.

When it comes time to assign the rights to the solution and use it, the company discovers that the participants work for a university. The participant wasn't aware of the university's lengthy IP policy document. Upon the inspection stage, the company discovers that in the university IP agreement, the institution makes claim to all inventions by employees which making it impractical and impossible to transfer the IP to the company.

The result is a disaster. The participants who suggested the solution won't get paid and the company doesn't get their solution after investing time, money and resources in the crowdsourcing process.

In this case, if the scenario is if the university IP policy was never actually disclosed or discovered, the participants would have signed the IP assignment, and the company would start using the solution in their product launch which they may spend millions of dollars of development. These kinds of issues can happen with universities, institutions and employment contracts. The fact is, using crowdsourcing, the participants are unknown, thus the companies don't know who they are dealing with which will always have risks.

Problem #5: Ideas vs. Solutions

If there are too many competitors involved in an event, the participants are less likely to put in a substantial amount of work when there are a lot of competitors.

“Where as the number of competitors increase, the average amount of effort that is put forth by any individual decreases.” (Wagon, 2014) For example if the risks ratios are high and reward ratio appear low, the chance to propose winning solutions are diminished.

“The result of this is that when you are crowdsourcing for solutions to problems using a large group versus engaging with a smaller number of competitors, what you typically end up with are ideas rather than solutions because there is typically a lot of work that is involved in transforming a mere idea into a fully developed, supported solution” (Wagon, 2014).

Crowdsourcing events are looking for technical solutions not brainstorming ideas. An idea without context or purpose is difficult to evaluate if this is a good idea to accomplish the problem. Companies also need to know how will the solution be implemented, and how exactly will it solve the problem.

On the other hand, a solution has a specific purpose to solve the problem.

Solutions are evaluated based on effectiveness, cost, risk and value. The most difficult part of job is scanning out good ideas that are not actual solutions. *“Many people would argue that an idea that is not completely thought through simply*

creates more work for the company, who needs to do all the heavy lifting of validating, supporting and thinking it through” (Wagon, 2014).

Wagon argued based on interviews with corporate executives, that he does not believe that conventional crowdsourcing has this balance to find the solutions. (Wagon, 2014) If crowdsourcing is only providing ideas, then it requires external resources to evaluate the best possible ideas and turn them into solutions. The only advantage of crowdsourcing it that it can generate a variety of ideas however so many that reduces the quality of what the process produces. (Wagon, 2014)

Problem #6: Burden on technical staff

Within the traditional approaches of crowdsourcing, there are two main issues; burden and scaling difficulties (Wagon, 2014).

When a company makes a decision to go public to outsource a solution, they may not have the resources and details necessary to make the process work. For example, small audiences of approximately 1000 participants are contacted by the company, and about 100 of them decide that they want to work on the problem. The company now needs to coordinate and address 100 peoples’ questions and evaluate 100 possible solutions to their proposed problem. The backend technical people will need to be able to answer all of their questions and review one hundred technical papers. These issues of both managing the

participants, and evaluating their solutions defeats the purpose of [using crowdsourcing](#) to begin with if not managed efficiently.

Evaluate similar products of Crowdsourcing (existing platform to hire contractors)

As previously mentioned, crowdsourcing is best solution for simple tasks. For example, crowdsourcing becomes a great option for web designers and designers in general to get some usable feedback on their work before making it public.

If one is looking for a new logo, hiring a professional designer is an option, but if it's a startup company with very limited budget crowdsourcing becomes a viable economic option for a company and an excellent work opportunity for the designer. The startup company can consider creating a competition on the crowdsourcing site to get a product for an affordable price.

Anybody who is building a huge library of photos, products, etc, can easily take advantage of crowdsourcing features. For building a new online shopping site, the users can use crowdsourcing and pay a small amount of money for people to describe, categorize or tag the inventory. Another example, if one needs a new website design, using crowdsourcing to ask your target audience to fill out a questionnaire regarding the new design which provides important feedback from the audience.

Crowdsourcing is a sound method to utilize when the company has limited resources, and is attempting to enter a very serious business venture such as developing a mobile game or creating corporate e-commerce site, which requires both expertise and intensive management.

The following examples are 13 popular crowdsourcing sites, which work on smaller scale projects and provide services to help on any of the related tasks. Each of the sites has their own individual navigation and interface design, however they all share the same kind of setup and requirement for users to sign up. The landing page design is very important to reflect on what kind of company it is, the branding of each company and information that the targeted users are looking for. The landing page represents the first impression and it affects the users to stay on the site or just bouncing out back to the search engine page.

Freelancer.com (<http://freelancer.com>)

Famous crowdsourcing site which offers online jobs to freelancers from around the world for everything from design to web development to programming. Companies or individuals post projects for a set price, and freelancers can bid on the jobs and offer their services.

The navigation and interface design of each of the crowdsourcing sites are simple and clear. Allow users to signup and setup their profiles. There are two types of users, the one who requests the job to be done and the contributors.

E lance (<http://elance.com>)

Similar to Freelancer.com, Elance is one of the most popular crowdsourcing sites online. Over 50,000 jobs posted on the site each month, ranging from programming to designing to writing. The navigation and interface design is very straightforward and user-friendly. Similar features are on all the crowdsourcing sites, all requires users to signup and setup their profiles. Mirroring the user system of Freelancer.com, there are also two types of users on this site, the one who requests the job to be done and the contributors.

United States Register Sign In

Elance FIND TALENT FIND WORK BUSINESS SOLUTIONS ABOUT US

Instant access to great talent

Over 500,000 rated & tested professionals to choose from.

- ✓ Staff up and down as needed
- ✓ Get candidates within hours
- ✓ Approve work before payment

[Learn More >](#)

Post Your Job
It's Free
Get Proposals in hours

Sign Up for Work
Access thousands of jobs

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ScriptLance (<http://www.scriptlance.com/>)

Designed for those looking to hire programmers and software developers, ScriptLance is a place where employers post a job and developers from around the world will bid for the work, with each offering their own rate. The navigation and interface design are little too text heavy on the landing page. Graphics or photos will attract first time users to read about the site and learn what the site does.

During the research period, ScriptLance actually revamped their design and changed their name to <https://www.freelancer.ca/> ScriptLance completely changed the interface design and layout. It is more up-to-date style and starts with two buttons: HIRE and WORK. Also, it expanded to more variety of freelancing work for creativity.

Guru (<http://www.guru.com/>)

Guru is the online service where jobs are offered to a wide variety of freelancers, who bid on projects ranging from programming to design to business management. Posting a job on Guru.com is free, while freelancers will pay certain percentage of their commission to Guru. Guru also recently expanded to include legal, finance, and engineering types of freelance jobs.

99designs (<http://99designs.com>)

A crowdsourcing marketplace for all sorts of graphic designs, where buyers post contests for anything from logo to website design, and a large pool of designers submit their designs and bid on the project in an open competition.

crowdSPRING (<https://www.crowdspring.com>)

crowdSPRING is a marketplace for graphic design. For instance, an ad agency will place a request for a logo or a band will request a CD cover design, and several designers will compete for the job. There is average of 110+ entries per project, and price per design project can range between \$200 to several thousand dollars.

Hatchwise (<http://www.hatchwise.com/>)

Hatchwise is similar to 99designs: design requests are submitted as competitions, where designers would submit and bid on the designs. It is especially useful for those looking for a logo design.

Feedback Army (<http://www.feedbackarmy.com/>)

Feedback Army offers to test your website with the use of crowds. The service charge is very affordable, the turnaround time is only 2 minutes and users will receive 10 responses from their reviewers

Utest (<http://www.utest.com/>)

Utest is a company that offers software testing which relies on crowdsourcing. Software makers use Utest's service to test their desktop or mobile software with large amounts of users. The tests include security testing, functional testing, usability testing etc.

UserTesting (<http://www.usertesting.com/>)

For an affordable price you can get video of a visitor discussing their thoughts as they use your site, and a written summary describing the problems they encountered.

Amazon Mechanical Turk (<https://www.mturk.com/mturk/welcome>)

One of the most popular crowdsourcing sites, useful for simple tasks like tagging photos, categorizing products, etc.

The screenshot shows the Amazon Mechanical Turk website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with tabs for 'Your Account', 'HITs', and 'Qualifications'. Below this is a secondary navigation bar with links for 'Introduction', 'Dashboard', 'Status', and 'Account Settings'. A yellow banner contains the text: 'Mechanical Turk is a marketplace for work. We give businesses and developers access to an on-demand, scalable workforce. Workers select from thousands of tasks and work whenever it's convenient. 162,609 HITs available. View them now.' Below the banner are two main sections. The left section, 'Make Money by working on HITs', describes HITs as individual tasks and lists benefits for workers: working from home, flexible hours, and payment for good work. It includes a flow diagram: 'Find an interesting task' (with a 'Find HITs Now' button) -> 'Work' (with a gear icon) -> 'Earn money' (with a dollar sign icon). The right section, 'Get Results from Mechanical Turk Workers', describes the process for requesters: 'Fund your account' (with a plus sign icon) -> 'Load your tasks' (with a document icon) -> 'Get results' (with a star icon). A 'Get Started' button is located below this flow.

InnoCentive (<http://www.innocentive.com/>)

InnoCentive is made for users looking to solve complicated questions, but it charge accordingly. The company claims to deliver breakthrough ideas and solutions at lower cost, in shorter time, and with less risk than previously possible.

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Where the World Innovates

Are you looking to solve problems and accelerate your innovation capability?

Drive Innovation »

Are you passionate about solving important problems that really matter?

Become A Solver »

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Challenge Title	Prize Amount
Fast Rope Glove Device Deadline: 12/17/2011 551 active solvers Referral award: \$1,500 USD	\$15,000 USD
Systems to Monitor Institutional Corruption Deadline: 11/08/2011 527 active solvers Referral award: \$800 USD	\$8,000 USD
Quantitative Model to Aid Strategy Decisions When Applying Open Innovation Deadline: 12/29/2011 405 active solvers Referral award: \$3,000 USD	\$30,000 USD
Model the Functional Molecular Networks in a Cancer Cell Deadline: 12/05/2011 406 active solvers Referral award: \$10,000 USD	\$100,000 USD

NEWSFLASH

InnoCentive Becomes a GSA Schedule Contractor

Today we announced that we've been awarded a GSA Schedule 541 4G, Challenges and Competitions Services. Federal public sector organizations can now conveniently purchase InnoCentive's products and services via the GSA's web portal that streamlines purchasing from scheduled contractors. With this milestone, InnoCentive becomes the first solutions provider on the schedule with a multi-channel open innovation platform and professional Challenge development services.

Innovation Exchange (<http://www.innovationexchange.com/>)

Another high-profile crowdsourcing site which operates in a similar fashion with InnoCentive. Innovators develop solutions and the best solutions are submitted for review by the team and the sponsor.

innovationexchange WHERE CREATIVITY IS THE CURRENCY

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Reach higher

IX puts you head and shoulders above your competition in innovation

Innovation Exchange (IX) is an online open innovation marketplace. It's where diverse community members from all over the world respond to challenges sponsored by Global 5000 companies and not-for-profit organizations.

2009 Entrepreneur 100 COMPANIES TO WATCH

Innovation Exchange is honored to be recognized by Entrepreneur magazine as one of the top 100 companies to watch out for.

PROPOSED BUSINESS MODEL FOR CROWDSOURCING

Problem Identification and Definition

For the average homeowners, the traditional way of searching for a home contractor usually involves the typical channels of the Yellow Pages or newspaper classified ads. Searching and selecting contractors to fix plumbing issues, leaky roofs, fence installation or any number of home maintenance issues can be a tedious and time consuming process for any homeowners. A financially responsible homeowner will contact several businesses in order to get different cost estimates.

Value Proposition

CrowdLiving Community is the solution for a new type of business model that uses a platform of connecting customers to contractors (C2C) or from contractors to customers in order to enhance business opportunities for both parties. A mutual benefit to both parties is that the platform provides a secure and safe forum to conduct business in. Both the customers and contractors will benefit from the time saved by using this more efficient search method. The contractors will be able to offer more services to a concentrated area of customers which will allow them to expand the amount of services offered thus gaining more customers. Reading and using the rating review system to evaluate contractors work and performance will enable potential customers to hire a reliable contractor. C2Cs will provide a safe and accurate forum for communication between clients, contractors and potential customers.

Target Family Profile

3 Typical Household Families in GTAs

Young Couples

- 20-30 years old
- Family income in Canada is \$76,000 per year
- Freehold Townhouse - 10-15 years old
- Lack of knowledge on home repair
- Lack of money

Dual Family Income Family without Children

- 25-35 years old
- Family income in Canada is \$100,000 – 150,000 per year
- Detach household - 10-15 years old
- Professionals seldom deal with home repair issues
- Money is not an main issue but lack of time of researching or looking for contractors

Dual Family Income Family with Children(s)

- 35-45 years old
- Family income in Canada is \$150,000 – 200,000 per year
- Detach double garage household - 10-15 years old
- Lack of time to complete home repair
- Working on budget

Local Contractors

Small business contractors in the local GTAs areas who work on short term contracts or individual project which offers services in plumbing, roof, fence installation or any number of home maintenance issues. They are using the traditional ways of posting advertisement such as using the classified pages in the newspaper, putting sign up after finishing a project at a location and adding their information on YellowPages. These local contractors mainly rely on referrals from previous clients.

Key Differentiation Pricing Charge

A local community household user and contractors will be free to register to the platform.

A typical household user can post a job request on the platform and describe the problem; what need to be fixed, the urgency of the job that needs to be done and what their desired budget is.

Contractors will receive notifications on new job request, they can decide if they want to bid on the jobs. If they are willing to provide the services, they can estimate what they will charge.

The user will receive one or multiple offers from bidding contractors then they

can evaluate by reading the contractors reviews, rating and service bureau information. This information can also be improved by researching the number of years the contractor has been operating.. They can select any contractor from the bidding list.

After each transaction, CrowdLiving will take 10% from the cost proposed by the selected contractor as a service charge.

Short Term and Long Term Business Goals

Short-term goals are to build a mockup of the platform and reach out to the target customers for a testing beta. Developing the first phase of selected targets to build the early-adapted communities. During the testing beta phase, the new business model will be consistently updating according to the users' feedback.

Long Term goals are to market the platform to reach both more localized areas and different communities in different locations.

Comparative Analysis Industry Scope and Nature

Contractors are waiting for customers; on the other hand, customers are searching for the contractors online. There is no medium to actually connect both parties. Contractors are limited to promoting on their webpages, putting signs after finishing a project at a household, posting advertisements on classified

pages. Customers are limited by online searches for contractors, which only consult large popular directory websites, Yellowpages or search for the company contact information or through referrals.

Competitors

There are two major informative websites, such as Helpedby which is the subsidiary of the Homeadvisor (<http://pro.helpedby.ca> and <http://www.homeadvisor.com>) are platforms helping customers to search for contractors services. The graphic design and branding of the sites is very professional using high quality images with an up-to-date web style. Navigation is easy to understand, very straightforward and user-friendly.

Customers and Customers Expectations

These sites benefit users by providing a platform for home improvement professionals to join the memberships to create the “Helpcard” with Trade credentials. This trustworthy information is very useful for users who wish to know about a professionals’ background.

Conversely both sites share the same disadvantages. The customers must use a traditional approach of searching for contractors then physically calling the contractor for an estimated price of service. Also, the search page is currently malfunctioning; the search result keeps popping up with the error 404.

Determine What the Key Success Factors are in Your Industry

The key success factors in contractors obtaining jobs are the accessibility of their information, their trade credentials to prove their trustworthiness to customers, their business locations and quintessentially their ability to connect to their customers.

CrowdLiving will be able to accomplish the five key success factors by acting as a platform to connect both parties to allow customers to search for the contractors' background information, verify their credentials, easy accessing communication, creating a community in a local area and will allow contractors to provide services in one area with many customers. This is going to enhance business opportunities, from customers to contractors (C2C) or from contractors to customers.

Business Model Canvas

Target Customers

Young Couples

Young couples that buy “fixer up” older townhouses but lack financial resources and knowledge on home repair. These types of households will heavily rely on handymen and local contractors for services.

Dual Income Family without Children

Couples in their 30's, who are childless and live in old houses. Couples are extremely busy with work. Money is not their main concern but lack of time to research and interview multiple contractors

Dual Income Family with Children(s)

Families with small kids who have a high income and live in old town houses.

Parents are busy with work and responsibilities of children. They don't have time to perform lengthy home repair jobs and are financially conscious of the costs of repairs.

Customer Problem or Challenge

Customers will benefit from the advantages of crowdsourcing by being able to get the best deals and services. Contractors will save on costs of travel; they will reach more clients in a concentrated location and be able to provide better services to their customers.

Value Proposition

Both the customers and contractors will benefit from the time saved using this more efficient of crowdsourcing to get better prices and building trust among the customers and contractors.

Revenue Generation

- Registration to the platform is totally free

- Community Users is free
- The final transaction will be charged 10% on the side of the contractor

Cost Structure

\$5000 of personal funds will be used to setup a platform for the website and mobile access. Expenses will include paying for a web server to host the platform, registration of the domain name. Also hiring an intern-programming student that will be paid minimum wages to develop the platform. The author of this paper will be paid minimum wage to handle the graphic design component of the site.

Profit Margin

After the site is constructed, it will be launched through an online community, it will take three months for the testing beta. Profit is not expected during the testing beta stage.

Customers to Contractors Approach (C2C)

The Customers to Contractors Approach is a new concept that will be built into a new business model using the crowdsourcing technologies. Customers can gather together to generate one service request. In one area, 10 customers could request the same types of services, such as roof renovation. CrowdLiving allows

them to create a community request by posting a job request. Contractors can bid on the project in a certain location. They are able to offer more services to a concentrated area which will allow them to improve upon the services offered to those customers enabling the contractors to build and gain local customers through referrals.

CrowdLiving will adapt the Helpcard system and take the advantages part to use the BETTER SERVICE BUREAU to verify the professionals for gaining the trustworthiness to the customers. A rating review system will be implemented to allow customers to evaluate contractors' work and performance. This will enable potential customers to hire a reliable contractor and let the contractors buildup their credentials through trustworthy reviews. C2Cs will provide a safe and accurate forum for communication between clients, contractors and potential customers.

Conclusion

As mentioned, O'Reilly defined Web 2.0 as a collaborative, interactive, participative version of the Web where individuals were no longer passive users of content that other had posted, but were the one generating the content themselves since 2004. (2014) Ten years of web technologies development, fast-paced live of the humanity world, daily users are heavily relying on the Internet from online shopping, academic research or looking for services. Web

technologies are important for businesses to get connected with their customers. CrowdLiving is taking the advantages of the crowdsourcing to develop a platform which operates by connecting customers to contractors (C2C) or contractors to customers in order to benefit local businesses to enhance opportunities for all users. The platform benefits both parties by providing a secure and safe forum to conduct business in. Both the customers and contractors will be able to take advantages of the time saving method of online connection. The contractors will be able to offer more services to a concentrated area of customers which will allow them to expand their services because of the time saved commuting to far away locations. This will enable to the contractors to gain more local customers. C2C provides a safe platform for communication and accurate reviews between clients, contractors and potential customers.

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